

Wind farm power short-term prediction using WRF model and Kalman filtering

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Abstract:

The growing wind power industry requires more reliable power forecasting due to higher penetration of this technology in electricity generation. Due to the stochastic behaviour of wind, additional tools for improving the electricity forecast are required. This research parameterizes WRF model for wind power forecasting in Qollpana wind farm -Bolivia. Qollpana is a wind farm over a very complex terrain and 2800 meters above sea level (masl) located on the Andes. Wind power forecasting is performed for different periods of the year, such as, January, April, June, and October. Finally, the results are improved using a Kalman filter and compared with the power generated in Qollpana wind farm. The simulated WRF results of energy generated in the wind farm showed between 50 and 30 % of error. However using a Kalman filter the errors diminished up to 10 % of the energy generated by the wind farm. The time of the highest errors (at sunlight time) suggests that topographic conditions play an important role in the wind farm electricity production.

Keywords:

Wind power plants, Renewable energy, Wind energy, Forecast, Wind potential.

1. Introduction

Wind energy is one of the most promising technologies for electricity generation to replace fossil-fuel consuming technologies. In this intend many countries along the world have introduced wind farms and along with some challenges related with transmission, dispatch and flexibility of the distribution system itself [1–3].

Bolivia has introduced the first wind farm in 2014 with only two wind turbine and nowadays there are ten wind turbines in total in the region called Qollpana [4]. The governmental electrical plan [5] proposes, as priority, the integration of renewable energy technologies, such as, wind, solar and hydro plants along the country, placing to Bolivia as the energy centre of South America [6].

Following the goals of this plan in recent years, solar plants and four wind farms are under construction distributed among Santa Cruz, Cochabamba and Tarija Departments.

One of the most important challenges of wind energy integration to the electricity system is the prediction on its generation. In this context Bolivia needs to adequate Numerical Weather Prediction models for its complex meteorology and topography. It is important to mention that Bolivia has a vast territory with different climate and topographic characteristic and it can be divided as Seiler et al. [7] in lowlands (<800 masl), Andean slopes (800-3200 masl), and highlands (Altiplano; >3200-6500 masl). The maximum annual mean temperatures decrease with altitude varying between 32 °C (in lowlands) and 16 °C (in highlands). There are wet and dry season that coincide with warmer austral summer and colder winter, respectively. Finally the rainfall varies decreasingly from north to south in the three zones described previously; where in average varies from the rainiest to the driest as follows, lowlands - Andean slopes – highlands [7].

The WRF model is meteorological mesoscale software with two dynamic cores, Advanced Research Weather (ARW) and Non-hydrostatic Mesoscale Model (NMM) [8], however the WRF-ARW has been the most used for research and operation. Some works showed that WRF model overestimate or underestimate the wind speed under diverse conditions. For example, Jimenez and Dudhia [9] conclude that the wind speed is overestimated over the plains and valleys and underestimate at the mountains and hills. In other case Carvalho et al. [10] determines that wind speed is overestimated at velocities lower than 8 m/s and underestimated when the wind velocity is higher than 8 m/s. For these reasons Kalman filter have been used as a tool to decrease the systematic error. Kalman filter has been used for data assimilation and improving weather forecast [11] and mainly for improving forecasts of wind speed and wind energy [12–14].

The main idea of the paper is evaluate to WRF-ARW model on wind energy prediction for Qollpana wind farm in Bolivia, this region has great importance because the installed capacity of the wind farm will be increased with additional 20 wind turbines. Furthermore, we analyse the effectiveness of Kalman filter in the wind power prediction.

2. Data and Methodology

2.1. Location of interest and dates of prediction

The selected site is Qollpana wind farm, because it is the unique operating farm in Bolivia. The dates were selected according to the different meteorological conditions in Bolivia. The dates are displayed in the Table 1 and the coordinates of Qollpana wind farm. All the simulations predicts to 12 hours ahead with different start time. January and April started at 06:00 UTC (2 AM local time); June and October started 12:00 UTC (8 AM local time). These different initial times were due to in June and October the wind speed was lower than 5 m/s before 12:00 UTC and under this conditions the wind farm produces insignificant power.

Table 1. Geographical information about the site in study

Name of the place	Latitude (°)	Longitude (°)	Elevation (m) asl	Date of analysis
Qollpana	17.631 S	65.279 W	2884	January 7, 2017
				April 19, 2017
				June 2, 2017
				October 8, 2016

2.2. Initial setup for WRF model

The simulations were executed with WRF-ARW v3.5.1 for short-term wind prediction with 50 km grid spacing and 41 vertical levels. The initial physics models in WRF-ARW are showed in the Table 2.

Table 2. WRF model settings

Model properties	Description	Details
Model	WRF-ARWv3.5.1	
Domain size	90x90	Grid size: 50 km
Domain limits	15-22 South latitude	62-66 West longitude
Microphysics	Thompson scheme	Thompson et al. [15]
Shortwave radiation	RRTMG shortwave schemes	Iacono et al. [16]
Longwave radiation	RRTMG longwave schemes	Iacono et al. [16]
Cumulus scheme	Kain–Fritsch Scheme	Janjić [17]
Surface Layer	Eta Similarity Scheme	Kain [18]

The simulations were developed for the site described in the Table 1.

2.3. Sensitivity of PBL schemes

To analyse the PBL effects in the different sites of study we executed simulations with WRF using two different combinations of PBL schemes. These are Yonsei University [19] and Mellor–Yamada–Janjic [17] PBL schemes.

2.4. Kalman filtering and wind power prediction

For Kalman filtering we follow the linear Kalman filtering process [20] and its characterized values are shown in the Table 3. We calculated the wind power of the whole wind farm using a third-order polynomial function, the coefficients and equation are presented in equation 1.

Table 3. Values for Kalman filtering

Variable	Value
System State Matrix	$\begin{bmatrix} 8 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$
Transformation Matrix	$[0.9 \quad 0]$
Input Matrix	$[5 \quad 0]$
Noise covariance	$\begin{bmatrix} 0.5 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.5 \end{bmatrix}$

In the eq. 1 wind power represents the power generated by Qollpana wind farm (MW) in function of average wind speed (u) in the wind farm.

$$\text{Wind Power [MW]} = 1.1689u^3 - 1.7099u^2 + 0.3973u - 0.0134 \quad (1)$$

The performance of the Kalman filtering is evaluated using two criteria. The error of total energy produced during the forecasted time (Eq. 2) and the normalised root mean square error (NRMSE) as explain equation 3 [12].

$$\text{Total energy [\%]} = \frac{\text{Forescated energy} - \text{Actual energy}}{\text{Actual energy produced}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{NRMSE [-]} = \frac{1}{P_{inst}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k (P_f(i) - P_o(i))^2} \quad (3)$$

where $P_f(i)$ denotes the electric power production forecasting value at time i , $P_o(i)$ is the electric power production observed value at time i , P_{inst} represents the rated installed power capacity in wind farm, k is the sample size.

3. Results and discussion

The results are organized as follows: the sensitivity of the two PBL schemes, Yonsei University and Mellor–Yamada–Janjic; the wind speed prediction and the Kalman filter over the wind, and finally the simulations with WRF-ARW and Kalman filtered predicted wind power.

Figure 1 shows a scatterplot of the two PBL schemes evaluated and those are quite similar one each other. Additionally the Fig. 1 displays that January and April accumulates the wind speed above 6 m/s and in June and October the wind speed is distributed between 5 and 10 m/s. These results are in concordance with the windiest months during 2017 in Bolivia [4].

Figure 1. Scatterplot of the two PBL schemes simulated, where YSU is Yonsei University Scheme and MYJ is Mellor–Yamada–Janjic Scheme.

The Fig 2 displays the simulated with WRF-ARW and Kalman filtered wind speed. The predicted wind speed with WRF-ARW in most of the cases is lower than the observed, however the best prediction corresponds to January 19, 2017. April for example has a good concordance between simulated-observed during 5-9 AM (local time); the cases of June 2, 2017 and October 8, 2016 the best results are during 8-10 AM (local time), after these hours the differences increase considerably.

Figure 2. Wind speed simulated with WRF-ARW compared with the observations and the Kalman filtered

The results showed in Fig. 2 suggest the high influence of local winds, such as, valley and slope winds [21]. Qollpana wind farm is located on a valley with complex terrain and the hours of large error support the hypotheses of valley and slope winds. In April the larger errors are at 06 UTC [2AM] (slope winds) and 18 UTC [2PM] (valley winds), those hours agree with the coolest and warmest hours of the day. A very similar events occur in June and October, the larger differences between simulated-observed are between 18 UTC [2PM] and 21 UTC [6PM] (valley winds). January has a good agreement between simulations and observations due to January is a cloudy month, for this reason the mountains and slope winds are weakly developed.

The Kalman filtering has improved the wind speed prediction for April, June and October. For the mentioned months the absolute error decreased between 2-5 m/s (Fig. 2. Green line). However January is the only one with over predicted wind speed.

Figure 3. Wind power predicted for different months compared with the observations, the power filtered (Filtered-PW) and the filtered over the wind speed filtered (Filtered-WS)

Figure 3 shows the different wind power predictions: the observed (blue line), simulated (red dashed line), Kalman filtered from the estimated power (green line), and Kalman filtered from the Kalman filtered wind speed (purple line). In general, the results show an improvement in the wind power predicted in all months, except in January, as is shown in Fig. 4. Additionally, there are large power differences between the simulated and Kalman filtered (Filtered-WS), because the power is highly sensitive to wind speed –as the Kalman filter increased the wind speed over the simulated, it will increase the wind power in the cubic of the wind speed.

Figure 4. Wind power error plots of the WRF-ARW simulations and using Kalman filter

Figure 4 and Table 4 summarise the improvement of the predictions using Kalman filter over the WRF-ARW simulations. In the best case –April– the error could decrease from 50 to 0.19 %, and for June and October the error drop from 30 to 10 % approximately. January is the unique case where the simulated results are better than Kalman filtered predictions.

Table 4. Error of the energy produced and NRMSE in the period of the simulations

	Energy-W [%]	Energy-K [%]	NRMSE-W [-]	NRMSE-K [-]
January	39.96	188.84	0.83	2.39
April	-50.56	0.19	1.85	0.98
June	-30.33	10.74	1.07	0.88
October	-34.19	-9.08	1.47	1.71

Additionally, Fig. 4 shows the NRMSE of the WRF-ARW simulations (NRMSE-W) and the improved with Kalman filtering (NRMSE-K). There are considerable NRMSE drop in April and June using Kalman filter: however, during October there is a slight increment in the NRMSE. These NRMSE results are higher compared with the value of 0.165 (NRMSE) obtained by Zhao et al. [12]. This difference is due to they used 4-nested domain compared with the 2-nested domain used in our work. However, to use 4-nested domain under our computational conditions could increase the simulation time from 30 minutes to 24 hours.

4. Conclusions

The present study was designed to determine the effect of Kalman filter over wind power predictions using WRF-ARW. According the results of this study, we could deduce, the following points: First, the PBL schemes analysed in this work (Yonsei University and Mellor–Yamada–Janjic) have insignificant effect in the wind speed simulations. Second, the Kalman filtering improved the wind power prediction in April, June and October, except for January. Finally, the main reason of high error in the simulations could be due to valley and slope winds in the zone.

The most important limitation lies in the computational capacity because we could decrease the grid size and increase the number of domains of the simulations, however this will increase the time of the simulations. In the future more research is needed for better understanding of WRF-ARW for prediction and implement more statistical tools to improve the simulation results for fast predictions.

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